

Course: ANTHRO 1201
Human Osteology & Bioarchaeology
Class Time: TR 10:30–11:45
Location: Zooarchaeology Lab,
Peabody 35B
Office Hours: By appointment
Instructor: Dr Jess Beck
Email: jbeck1@fas.harvard.edu

Santiago Caruso – Wunderkammer

Knowledge of human osteology is key for fields such as archaeology, biological anthropology, forensic anthropology, anatomy, and medicine. This course introduces students to human skeletal anatomy and the field of bioarchaeology, the study of human skeletal remains from archaeological sites. The first half of the course provides an introduction to skeletal anatomy for anthropologists and biologists and covers the entire human skeleton, with sections on growth, development, and pathology. The skeletal anatomy of select non-human mammals is used to demonstrate the functional morphology of each bone. This second half of the course introduces students to the basic methods of human skeletal analysis, including assessing the age, sex, health, and stature of an individual using their bones. The grade for this course will be based on a combination of participation, quizzes, larger assessments, and the maintenance of a “bone notebook” in which students sketch and describe individual skeletal elements. Students taking the course at the graduate level will also submit a final research paper that examines a topic of bioarchaeological significance in a region and/or period pertinent to their own academic research.

Learning Outcomes

By the end of the course students will have experience:

- Identifying individual bones
- Recognizing features and landmarks
- Understanding how bones articulate
- Examining bones for signs of pathology
- Differentiating human and non-human bones
- Estimating age, sex, and stature from human remains
- Estimating how many individuals are represented by a given set of remains

Class Behavior

This class includes handling real human bones and looking at images of dead bodies. All students are expected to maintain high levels of professionalism in this course, which includes respect for the dead and for each other. You may not take personal photos of the real human remains. You may not handle food or drink while working with any museum collections. Any disrespectful behaviors will result in a penalty on your overall course grade and may result in removal from the course.

Readings

The required textbook is Steele and Bramblett (1988) *The Anatomy and Biology of the Human Skeleton*. Additional readings will be posted on the course Canvas site.

Grading

This course may not be taken pass/fail. Your grade in this course will be based on four primary components:

Engagement (20%)	Quizzes (15%)
Assessments (50%)	Bone Notebook (15%)

Final course grades will be assigned using a 100-point scale. Harvard does not assign a grade of A+; an “A” grade is ≥ 95 points. A failing grade is ≤ 62 points. Grades will be rounded up or down to the nearest integer.

A- = 90-94

B+ = 87-89

B = 83-86

B- = 80-82

C+ = 77-79

C = 73-76, etc., etc.

Undergraduate/Graduate Course Difference:

Students taking the course at the graduate level will also complete a final research paper that examines a topic of bioarchaeological significance in the region of their dissertation research. An alternate region may also be selected if pertinent.

Engagement (15%)	Quizzes (10%)
Assessments (45%)	Bone Notebook (10%)
Final Research Paper (20%)	

COVID-19 NOTE: I recognize that we are living through a global pandemic and that as a result there may be times during the semester when you need to quarantine or miss a class for COVID-related reasons. I will be as flexible as possible when making accommodations. If you require accommodations for COVID-related reasons, please let me know as soon as possible and we will find a way for you to make up the work.

Grading Structure

Engagement (20%): A weekly attendance sheet will circulate. It is your responsibility to sign the attendance sheet—if you are not able to do so at the beginning of class, you are responsible for asking for the attendance sheet at the end of class. However, simply showing up is not sufficient to achieve the full mark. Active demonstration that you are engaged with the course material, including participating in labs, contributing to class discussion, and diligently working on your Bone Notebook over the course of the semester, will also be factored into this grade. Your overall course engagement will receive a single grade based on the following criteria: absent for more than five in-person classes or remote equivalents (0 pts), passive (10 pts), occasionally active (15 pts), or regularly active (20 pts). If you are having issues with accruing multiple absences for emergency reasons, please contact me to let me know—see the COVID-19 note above.

Quizzes (15%): There are six quizzes in this class. The quizzes will take between 10–15 minutes each and will incorporate a variety of question formats, including short answer, multiple choice, and identification. Your lowest quiz grade will be dropped, so quizzes are worth 3% each. Treat these quizzes as practice for your assessments—they are an opportunity for you to test your skills under time pressure and identify areas that you need to work on. There are over 200 bones in the human body; cramming is a bad strategy.

Bone Notebook (15%): Sketching individual elements from several different views is a key strategy that helps novice osteologists identify features while increasing their familiarity with the human skeleton. Time will be set aside to sketch the bones or teeth we are learning; these notebooks will also act as useful repositories for identification and siding tricks and as comprehensive notes for review before exams. At the end of the course, your notebooks will be collected and graded. A detailed guide to your bone notebooks is provided on the first day of class and will be available as a pdf on Canvas.

Assessments (50%): There will be 2 exam-style assessments in this course; the assessments will incorporate a variety of question formats, including visual identification of bones, multiple choice, and written responses. The exams are worth 25% each for students taking the course at the undergraduate level.

Late Assignments

Late assignments will be docked by one point for the first 24 hours, then two points per each subsequent day. Please see the COVID-19 note for details.

Expectations of Academic Integrity

In this course you will collaborate with other students during activities and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own worksheets and written assignments, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with Harvard academic policy. Please consult the [Harvard Honor Code](#), the section in the [Harvard College Handbook on Academic Integrity](#), and the [Harvard Guide for Using Sources](#) during the first week of class.

Accessibility Accommodations

Any student needing academic adjustments or accommodations is requested to present their letter from the [Accessible Education Office \(AEO\)](#) and speak with the professor by the end of the second week of the term. Failure to do so may result in the course head's inability to respond in a timely manner. All discussions will remain confidential, although AEO may be consulted to discuss appropriate implementation.

Title IX Responsibilities

All Harvard faculty members are “responsible employees;” if you inform a member of the faculty about a situation involving sexual harassment, sexual assault, relationship abuse, or stalking, they must share that information with the Title IX Coordinator. After a notification, the Title IX office will only provide outreach by email, meaning that you will control how your case will be handled—you do not have to read or reply to the email. It is entirely your decision whether or not to pursue a formal complaint.

Schedule of Quizzes, Assessments, and Due Dates

Assignment	Date
Quiz 1: Ethics, Skull & Teeth	Tuesday, 08 February
Quiz 2: Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle	Tuesday, 15 February
Quiz 3: Upper Limb & Pelvic Girdle	Tuesday, 01 March
Quiz 4: Lower Limb	Tuesday, 08 March
Assessment 1	Thursday, 10 March
Bone Notebook	Thursday, 24 March
Quiz 5: Estimating Age	Tuesday, 12 April
Quiz 6: Estimating Sex	Tuesday, 19 April
Assessment 2	Tuesday, 26 April
Final Research Paper	Wednesday, 27 April

Schedule of Course Meetings Held in Peabody B8

Meeting (Week/Day)	Date	Category	Topic
2.1	Tuesday, 01 February	Practical	The Skull
2.2	Thursday, 03 February	Lecture & Practical	The Teeth
3.2	Thursday, 10 February	Practical	The Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle
4.2	Thursday, 17 February	Practical	The Arm & Forearm + The Wrist
5.2	Thursday, 24 February	Practical	The Hand & Fingers + Pelvic Girdle
6.2	Thursday, 03 March	Practical	The Lower Limb
7.1	Tuesday, 08 March	Open Review	Open Review for A1
7.2	Thursday, 10 March	Assessment	Assessment 1
10.2	Thursday, 07 April	Practical	Estimating Age
11.2	Thursday, 14 April	Practical	Assessing Sex
12.2	Thursday, 21 April	Open Review	Open Review for A2
13.1	Tuesday, 26 April	Assessment	Assessment 2

VIRTUAL RESOURCES

At times this semester we may need to think outside the box and get creative about learning osteology. These are resources you can use to hone and practice your skills outside of lab.

John Hawks Laboratory (UW Madison)
– Virtual Labs in Biological Anthropology

JOHN HAWKS LABORATORY

Human evolution and genetics

<https://hominin.anthropology.wisc.edu/virtual-labs.html>

A variety of virtual anthropology labs are available on this website, which is of particular utility for students interested in biological anthropology and paleoanthropology. The first five labs—Regions of the Skeleton, Regions of the Cranium, Morphology of the Femur, Morphology of the Pelvis, and Pelvic Sexual Dimorphism—are useful resources.

eSkeletons (University of Texas at Austin)

<http://eskeletons.org/>

eSkeletons is an online osteology database aimed at teaching skeletal anatomy. It allows you to filter by species, specimen, bone, and view. This is an excellent resource for the comparative anatomy of primates. For example, if you want to compare photographs of a human hamate (one of the bones in the wrist) to a gibbon hamate, you can easily do so using the eSkeletons database.

Digitized Diseases (University of Bradford)

<http://www.digitiseddiseases.org/alpha/>

“an open access resource featuring human bones which have been digitised using 3D laser scanning, CT and radiography. The resource focuses on a wide range of pathological type specimens from archaeological and historical medical collections, specifically examples of chronic diseases which affect the human skeleton for which many of the physical changes are often not directly observable within clinical practice. [Includes] high fidelity photo-realistic digital representations of 3D bones that can be viewed, downloaded and manipulated on their computer, tablet or smartphone.” This is fantastic for students interested in bioarchaeology, especially skeletal pathology and trauma. Caveat: As of February, 2021 the site was experiencing some glitches due to a server upgrade.

MorphoSource BETA

Morphosource (Duke University)

<https://www.morphosource.org/>

Morphosource compiles 2D and 3D data from a variety of museums, researchers, and colleges for a wide variety of species. As of February 2021, Morphosource has 235 human scans, and you can zoom and rotate the scans in their online portal. For quick reference, here is the taxonomic categorization of humans:

Kingdom–Animalia | Phylum–Chordata | Class–Mammalia | Order–Primates

Family–Hominidae | Genus–Homo | Species–sapiens

Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History 3D Collection

Smithsonian
National Museum of Natural History

<https://3d.si.edu/collections/hominin-fossils>

The Smithsonian has a 3D collection of CT or laser-scanned artifacts, fossils, and animals that you can view, rotate, and interact with on their website. The full collection can be found here <https://humanorigins.si.edu/evidence/3d-collection>, and the hominin fossils are linked above. The fossil scans are all of crania or mandibles, and there are a few specimens of Homo sapiens in the collection. This is a good site for students interested in biological anthropology, particularly paleoanthropology.

The Radiologist Instagram Page

<https://www.instagram.com/theradiologistpage>

Dr Naveen Sharma—a UK-based Consultant Radiologist—provides a resource that helps anyone learn more about radiology. Radiographs are labelled in detail, and there are lots of memes! This is a useful resource for students considering pre-med or a career in radiology.

Human Osteology Resources (Wichita State University)

WICHITA STATE
UNIVERSITY

<https://libraries.wichita.edu/c.php?g=120021&p=782022>

This library page lists a variety of resources for learning osteology and can be used to further your interests in anatomy, human biology, paleopathology, and radiology.

3D4MEDICAL from ELSEVIER

3D 4 Medical (Elsevier)

<https://3d4medical.com/>

NOTE: COSTS \$35 FOR ANNUAL STUDENT LICENSE. I downloaded the free trial of this recently and it is a wonderfully detailed virtual resource that allows you to examine and rotate individual elements, and add layers of connective tissue muscle, nerves, blood, etc. Key features and muscle attachment sites are identified for each bone. A particularly useful resource for students following the pre-med track.

Class Schedule, Meeting Locations, and Reading List

Note: The readings assigned for a particular day should be read **before** that day, to ensure that you are prepared for the discussion or activities. I reserve the right to change this schedule if I believe such a change is pertinent to our safety and/or the direction of the course. Please carefully note where each class meeting is held; locations are listed in parentheses after meeting dates. The dates we are meeting in Peabody B8 are also listed on p.4 of the syllabus.

Week 1: Anatomical Terminology, Bone Biology & Ethics + The Skull

Tuesday, 25 January (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

Lecture: Bone Biology, Anatomical Terminology & Ethics

Reading(s): Bernstein, 2018; Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 1: Introduction to the Study of the Human Skeleton + Chapter 2: Bone Biology (16 pp.)

Tuesday, 27 January (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

Lecture: The Skull + Dr Morgan Visit

Visitor: Dr Michèle Morgan, Peabody Museum Curator of Osteology and Paleoanthropology

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 3: The Skull (49 pp.)

Week 2: The Skull & Teeth

Tuesday, 01 February (Peabody Museum, B8)

Practical: The Skull

Reading(s): None

Tuesday, 03 February (Peabody Museum, B8)

Lecture and Practical: The Teeth

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 4: The Dentition (40 pp.)

Week 3: The Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle

Tuesday, 08 February (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

QUIZ 1

Lecture: The Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 5: The Vertebral Column (26 pp.)

Thursday, 10 February (Peabody Museum, B8)

Practical: The Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 6: The Chest and Shoulder Girdle (41 pp.)

Week 4: The Arm & Forearm + The Wrist

Tuesday, 15 February (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

QUIZ 2

Lecture: The Arm & Forearm + The Wrist

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 7: The Arm (19 pp.)

Thursday, 17 February (Peabody Museum, B8)

Practical: The Arm, Forearm & Wrist

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 8: The Wrist, Hand, and Fingers (16 pp.)

Week 5: The Hand & Fingers + The Pelvic Girdle

Tuesday, 22 February (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

Lecture: The Hand & Fingers + The Pelvic Girdle

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 9: The Pelvic Girdle (25 pp.)

Thursday, 24 February (Peabody Museum, B8)

Practical: The Hand & Fingers + The Pelvic Girdle

Reading(s): None

Week 6: The Lower Limb

Tuesday, 01 March (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

QUIZ 3

Lecture: The Lower Limb

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 10: The Leg (26 pp.)

Thursday, 03 March (Peabody Museum, B8)

Practical: The Lower Limb

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 11: The Ankle, Foot, and Toes (20 pp.)

Week 7: Review and Assessment 1

Tuesday, 08 March (Peabody Museum, B8)

QUIZ 4

Topic: Open Period: Review for Assessment 1

Reading(s): None

Thursday, 10 March (Peabody Museum, B8)

ASSESSMENT 1

MID-SEMESTER RECESS MARCH 12-21

Week 8: Growth, Development & Pathology + Comparative Functional Anatomy

Tuesday, 22 March (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

Lecture: Growth, Development & Pathology

Reading(s): Goodman and Martin, 2002 (38 pp.)

Thursday, 24 March (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

BONE NOTEBOOK DUE IN CLASS

Lecture and Practical: Comparative Functional Anatomy

Reading(s): Beisaw, 2013 (55 pp.)

Week 9: Forensic Anthropology & Bioarchaeology + Estimating Subadult Age

Note: Dr Beck will be attending a conference this week. For the first class, you will watch a documentary on forensic anthropology that is available on YouTube. For the second class, you will watch a pre-recorded lecture given by Dr Beck on estimating subadult age.

Tuesday, 29 March 2021 (Remote class)

Topic: Forensic Anthropology & Bioarchaeology

Video: Diane France, *The Bone Detective* <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KcnGybzFhjM>

Reading(s): None

Thursday, 31 March, 2021 (Remote class)

Lecture (Pre-recorded): Estimating Subadult Age

Reading(s): Scheuer and Black, 2004 (22 pp.)

Week 10: Estimating Adult Age + Age Estimation Practical

Tuesday, 05 April 2021 (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

Lecture: Estimating Adult Age

Reading(s): Byers, 2017, Chapter 9: Estimation of Age at Death (pp.218–236).

Thursday, 07 April 2021 (Peabody Museum, B8)

Practical: Estimating Age

Reading(s): Read the following sections in Buikstra & Ubelaker 1994:

- Chapter 3: Documentation of Age Changes (pp. 21–38)
- Chapter 4: Immature Remains: Maturation and Measurement (pp. 39–43)
- Chapter 5: Dental Data Collection I (pp. 47–53)

Week 11: Assessing Sex + Assessment of Sex Practical

Tuesday, 12 April (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

QUIZ 5

Lecture: Assessing Sex

Reading(s): Stone, 2012 (3 pp.); Hollimon, 2011 (14 pp.)

Thursday, 14 April (Peabody Museum, B8)

Practical: Assessing Sex

Reading(s): White and Folkens, 2005, Chapter 19: Determination of Sex (pp.386–398).

Week 12: Estimating Stature & Assessing Taphonomy, Trauma & MNI + Open Review

Tuesday, 19 April (Peabody Museum, 35B, Zooarchaeology Laboratory)

QUIZ 6

Lecture: Estimating Stature, Evaluating Trauma, Taphonomy, and MNI

Reading(s): Beck et al., 2015 (10 pp.); White and Folkens, 2005, Chapter 19: Estimation of Stature (pp.398–400)

Thursday, 21 April (Peabody Museum, B8)

Topic: Open Period: Review for Assessment 2

Readings: Byers 2017, Chapter 11: Death, Trauma, and the Skeleton (20 pp.)

Week 13: Assessment 2

Tuesday, 26 April (Peabody Museum, B8)

Reading(s): ASSESSMENT 2

Reading List

- Beck, J., I. Ostericher, G. Sollish & De León, J. (2015). Animal scavenging and scattering and the implications for documenting the deaths of undocumented border crossers in the Sonoran Desert. *Journal of Forensic Sciences* 60(S1): S11–S20.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1556-4029.12597>
- Beisaw, A. M. (2013). What bone is it? In *Identifying and interpreting animal bones: A manual* (pp. 47–102). Texas A&M University Press.
- Bernstein, R. E. (2018, May 18). The skeleton in my closet. *The New York Times*.
<https://www.nytimes.com/2018/05/18/well/family/the-skeleton-in-my-closet.html>
- Byers, S. N. (2017). *An introduction to forensic anthropology*. 5th Ed. Routledge.
- Buikstra, J. E., & Ubelaker, D.H. (Eds.). (1994). *Standards for data collection from human skeletal remains*. Arkansas Archaeological Survey Research Series No. 44. Arkansas Archaeological Survey.
- Goodman, A.H., & Martin, D.L. (2002). Reconstructing health profiles from skeletal remains. In R.H. Steckel & J.C. Rose (Eds.), *The backbone of history: Health and nutrition in the western hemisphere* (pp.11–60). Cambridge University Press.
- Hollimon, S.E. (2011). Sex and gender in bioarchaeological research: Theory, method, and interpretation. In S. C. Agarwal & B. A. Glencross (Eds.). *Social bioarchaeology* (pp. 149–182). Wiley-Blackwell.
- Scheuer, L., & Black, S. (2004). Juvenile skeletal remains: Provenance, identification, and interpretation. In *The juvenile skeleton* (pp. 1–22). Elsevier Academic Press.
- Steele, D.G., & Bramblett, C.A. (1988). *The anatomy and biology of the human skeleton*. Texas A&M University Press.
- Stone, P. K. (2012). A bioarchaeology of sex and gender: What is the difference and why is it important? *The SAA Archaeological Record* 12(2),38–40.
- White, T. D, & Folkens, P. A. (2005). *The human bone manual*. Elsevier Academic Press.

Bone Broke Blog

When I was in grad school and had a little more time and a lot more energy, I maintained a blog. I haven't written any new posts for years, but the blog contains a vast repository of osteological and bioarchaeological information, generally conveyed in a light-hearted or humorous manner that is intended to help novice practitioners remember complex osteological terminology and morphology. I still return to some of my siding and identification posts when I am in the field and refreshing my own osteological knowledge. The blog can be found at www.bonebroke.org. I have identified a number of relevant posts on the next page, categorized by topic or anatomical region.

Anatomical Terminology

Standard Anatomical Position: [Bioarch Vocab: SAP](#)

Abduction and Adduction: [Bioarch Vocab: Abduction and Adduction](#)

Supination: [Bioarch Vocab: Supination](#)

Features and Pathology

Glenoid fossa: Bioarch Vocab: [Glenoid Fossa](#)

Nutrient foramen: [Bioarch Vocab: Nutrient Foramen](#)

Caries: Bioarch Vocab: [Caries](#)

Calculus: [Bioarch Vocab: Calculus](#)

Skull

Splanchnocranium: [Bioarch Vocab: Splanchnocranium](#)

Temporal: [Osteomenagerie 3: The petrous portion of the temporal bone](#)

Temporal: [Palpable anatomy: How to identify and side an isolated zygomatic process](#)

Parietals: [How to identify and side parietal bones](#)

Teeth

All teeth: [Identifying human teeth: Human dentition cheat sheet](#)

Vertebral Column

Vertebrae: [Osteomenagerie 7: The Vertebrae](#)

Vertebrae: [Cake or...superior articular facets?](#)

Chest & Shoulder Girdle

Ribs: [Orienting and siding regular ribs](#)

Pelvic Girdle

Innominate: [Hip hip hooray: Orienting and identifying features of the os coxae](#)

Arm, Wrist & Hand

Humerus: [Feeling shafted? Tips for identifying humeral shaft fragments](#)

Radius: [That's so rad: Identifying and siding the radius](#)

Phalanges: [Gotta hand it to you: identifying manual and pedal phalanges](#)

Scaphoid: [Osteomenagerie 2: The scaphoid](#)

Lunate: [In Honor of the "Super Moon" – Identifying and siding the lunate](#)

Carpals: [Osteomenagerie 4: The capitate](#)

Pisiform: [Osteomenagerie 5: The pisiform](#)

Hamate: [Identifying and siding the hamate](#)

Leg, Ankle & Foot

Tibia: [Tibial pursuit: How to identify and side the tibia](#)

Femur: [Get a leg up on the competition: Tips for identifying femoral shaft fragments](#)

Patella: [A guide to quickly siding the patella](#)

Navicular: [Osteomenagerie 1: The navicular](#)

Calcaneus: [Osteomenagerie 6: Tips for siding the calcaneus](#)

Cuneiforms: [Merely a cuneiformality: Identifying and siding the cuneiforms](#)

Pedal Phalanges: [Gotta hand it to you: identifying manual and pedal phalanges](#)